

Enhancing Misogyny Classification in Code-mixed Hindi-English with Rationales

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Abstract. Online hate speech is a critical concern in the digital age. Deep learning models have been particularly useful in automatic hate speech detection, but lack transparency and interpretability due to their black-box nature. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is an area of research that focuses on making black-box models more interpretable by humans, and can also uncover unintended biases in the model. In the study, a novel dataset has been introduced for misogyny classification in code-mixed Hindi English with the rationales for classification highlighted in the form of binary token masks. Two deep learning based architectures, Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (BiRNN) and multilingual Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (mBERT) have been fine-tuned on the data, with and without rationale supervision. The study found that rationale supervised training moderately improved the performance of both deep learning architectures on the standard performance metrics such as accuracy, macro-F1, and explainability metrics.

Keywords: natural language processing · hate speech detection · misogyny · transformers · Hinglish.

1 Introduction

Social media has exacerbated the problem of hate speech due to the perceived anonymity and widespread reach of the internet [37]. Hate speech is any form of language that demeans or belittles a person on the basis of identity factors such as race, gender, nationality, and sexual orientation [31]. Misogyny is the hatred of and prejudice against women, and is rampant in online discourse [13]. This type of abuse can be highly detrimental to the mental health of the target [1], reinforce harmful and archaic stereotypes, and even escalate into real-world violence [6]. The high volume of social media content makes manual moderation impossible, and automated tools are necessary to alleviate the workload of content moderators [37]. Therefore, developing strategies to address online hate speech is of critical importance, from both social and technical perspectives [30]. Natural Language Processing (NLP), a branch within the broader

area of Artificial Intelligence (AI), is an essential tool for automatic detection of hate speech, owing to its capacity to analyse large amounts of text and draw insights from it [5]. Studies have explored hate speech detection using models and NLP tools in numerous languages such as English, Spanish, Italian, Hindi, and Marathi [18] [12]. Approaches range from traditional rule-based systems which are rigid and use pre-defined profanity lists [29], to current state-of-the-art transformers-based models [20], which can capture semantic meaning and context from unstructured text. However, research in hate speech detection in code-mixed languages is scarce, due to various linguistic complexities, lack of data sets and resources, and insufficient social and cultural context [33]. India, which is home to over 451 million YouTube users [28] and 64.1 million Reddit users [2], has a rich linguistic diversity. Online communication usually combines features from one or more languages for ease of typing, a phenomenon called code mixing [27]. ‘Hinglish’ is a code-mixed language that blends elements from Hindi and English, and is one of the most frequently used informal languages online in India [34]. In recent years, studies have explored hate speech identification in code-mixed languages with great success [3], but struggle to perform more fine-grained hate speech detection [26]. The lack of explainability and transparency in hate speech classifiers is also a concern, and AI models sometimes pick up on spurious correlations to misclassify a sentence [33] [14]. Several explainability methods, such as Local Interpretable Model Agnostic Explanations (LIME) [24] and Shapely Additive Values (SHAP) [17] are model agnostic, and can be used to examine the decision-making process of hate speech classifiers. In this study, a novel data set collected from Reddit³ has been introduced for binary misogyny classification in code-mixed Hindi English. Rationales are short spans of text from the input that are highlighted as the most important, and are used to justify the model’s decision. Ethical permission has been obtained from the host institute to perform binary annotation and rationale marking by two annotators.

Rationales have been incorporated into fine-tuning BiRNN and mBERT, based on the study [19], to allow comparison between two differing architectures⁴. Future work will explore additional model architectures. The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 outlines the underlying motivation behind conducting this study. Section 3 covers the literature in the areas of the study. Section 4 covers the methodology implemented in this study. Section 5 records and analyzes the findings of the study, and performs statistical testing to determine significance of the results. Section 6 discusses the research questions and hypothesis in light of the study findings, and Section 7 presents the conclusion of the study.

³ <https://www.reddit.com>

⁴ <https://github.com/hate-alert/HateXplain>

2 Motivation

Previous studies that have explored hate speech detection in code mixed languages have identified several challenges, including the lack of a formal structure [4], inconsistent spelling and grammar, lack of cultural and social context [37].

Hypothesis 1: Incorporating human-annotated rationales during training of misogyny classifiers improves model performance on empirical metrics.

1. RQ-1: How does the incorporation of rationales impact the predictive performance of misogyny classifiers on classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and macro-F1 score?

Hypothesis 2: Incorporating human-annotated rationales during training of misogyny classifiers improves model performance on explainability metrics.

1. RQ-2: How does the incorporation of rationales impact the performance of misogyny classifiers on plausibility and faithfulness metrics?

3 Related Work

The section will cover the latest advances in hate speech detection, XAI and its evaluation frameworks for under-resourced and code-mixed languages.

3.1 Hate Speech Detection

NLP models have an inherent advantage over human content moderators due to the ability to quickly analyse a large volume of unstructured text without any cognitive load [7]. Deep learning models are a more recent development in artificial intelligence, and models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [25], and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs) [22] networks, have surpassed the performance of machine learning algorithms on many NLP tasks. The transformer architecture [32], which is a deep learning-based architecture, has demonstrated excellent performance on NLP tasks such as sentiment analysis [36]. The HASOC shared task has been conducted almost every year since 2019, and has covered a range of languages such as English, code-mixed Hinglish, Marathi, and German [26] [18]. The Automatic Misogyny Identification (AMI) shared task [11] is focused on misogyny identification and categorization into subtypes of misogynistic behavior such as Discredit, Stereotype and Objectification, Sexual Harassment, and Threats of Violence [12]. Shared tasks and challenges such as HASOC [18] and TRAC [15] stimulate research in the field, by introducing benchmark data sets, promoting the competitive development of classifiers, and supporting international collaboration between researchers.

3.2 Explainable Artificial Intelligence

XAI techniques such as LIME, SHAP, and IG can be applied to hate speech classifiers to ensure that they are not misclassifying statements based on biased and insignificant features, and can build trust and accountability [35]. HateXplain [19] is a benchmark resource for explainable hate speech detection collected from Twitter and GAB, which also consists of the human rationale for prediction, which reduced unintended bias in the models. The study by [14] introduces Deephatexplainer, which is an explainable hate speech detection framework for Bengali, and highlighted that models that perform well on empirical metrics are not the most interpretable for humans. The evaluation of XAI techniques is crucial to determine their reliability, robustness, and evaluate their fidelity to the original model [10]. Despite these recent advancements, XAI remains under-explored for code-mixed and under-resourced NLP systems.

4 Methodology

This section discusses the methodology of the study in detail.

4.1 Dataset

Data collection has been performed from a public subreddit via Reddit’s API after obtaining ethical permission from the host institute. The text is in the following form: title of the post, body of the post, and subsequent comments. Out of a total of 6,022 samples, each data point has been annotated by 2 independent annotators. In cases of disagreement between two annotations, the data points and the final label were decided by a 3rd independent annotator through majority voting. A Cohen’s kappa of 0.87 was observed between the labels assigned by first and second annotators. The data has been categorized for binary classification into two classes: NOT (Not misogynistic) - 2710 samples, and MGY (misogynistic) - 3312 comments. An example of a misogynistic comment from the data is ‘Wo bhi saali gutterchaap sasti raand hai’, which roughly translates to ‘She too is a cheap prostitute from the gutter.’. Data has been converted into lowercase. The methodology used for rationale incorporation in misogyny classifiers has been inspired by the work of Matthew et al. [19]. The rationales highlighted by the annotator have been converted into token-level masks, where ‘1’ represents the tokens highlighted as rationales for misogyny, and ‘0’ all other tokens. For example, in the statement ‘Women should not drive’, if the tokens ‘Women’, ‘not’, and ‘drive’ were selected as rationales, then the mask is : [1, 0, 1, 1].

4.2 Model Training

For MGY comments, the token-level masks provided by the two annotators are added and normalized using a temperature-scaled softmax, yielding a soft

ground-truth attention distribution. For the ‘NOT’ comments, each token is assigned an equal attention weight of $1/\text{sentence length}$. The parameter used for temperature scaling, τ , is a tunable parameter, but has been set to 0.5 for this study. Parameter tuning was not performed for τ due to resource constraints. After obtaining the ground truth rationales through applying softmax, the input embeddings, labels, and the ground truth rationale vectors are fed into the models. The model architectures have been described in Table 1. There are two training scenarios:

Standard Fine-tuning This is the standard (label-only) training of BiRNN, BiRNN-Attn, and mBERT from Table 1. For BiRNN-based architectures, word representations using 200-dimensional GloVe embeddings⁵ are initialized, and fine-tuned during training. Minimal pre-processing has been performed for mBERT, as transformer-based models work better with noisy and unclean data [8]. For mBERT, a learning rate of $2e-5$, 2 training epochs, batch size of 16, and a maximum sequence length of 100 was selected. For BiRNN, a learning rate of $1e-3$, 3 training epochs, batch size of 32, and maximum sequence length of 100 is selected after some fine-tuning. mBERT and BiRNN have been fine-tuned 10 times with different seeds to capture variance, and the mean score has been recorded. Hyper-parameter tuning has been performed by altering the learning rate, batch size, sequence length, and number for epochs. BiRNN-Attn is the basic BiRNN architecture, with an attention layer which assigns importance score to each token after the sequential layer has been implemented as from [16]. The attention layer computes a token-level attention vector using a context vector to highlight important words. These weights are then multiplied with the output hidden units from the sequential layer, and summed to form a sentence-level representation, which is then passed through two fully connected layers.

Rationale Supervised Training In this scenario, the ground-truth rationales are utilized to align the model’s internal attention mechanisms with the human-annotated ground truth rationales, as shown in Figure 1. In case of mBERT-Ratn, in addition to standard fine-tuning, the attention weight corresponding to the [CLS] token is extracted from the last layer and compared with the ground truth attention to calculate the masked cross entropy loss. The [CLS] token aggregates information from the entire input sequence, and is used by transformers to perform classification. This resulting attention supervision loss is then added to the classification loss, with an attention weighted by an attention coefficient λ . Similarly for BiRNN-Ratn, a cross-entropy loss is computed between the attention layer output and the ground truth attention to train the attention layer outputs. The combined loss function is:

$$L_{\text{total}} = L_{\text{pred}} + \lambda \cdot L_{\text{att}} \quad (1)$$

where L_{pred} is the standard classification loss and L_{att} is the attention loss, which is the cross-entropy loss between the human-annotated rationale distribution

⁵ <https://nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/>

Fig. 1: Ground Truth Attention Calculation and Rationale Supervised Training

and the model attention distribution. The parameter λ controls the impact of rationale supervision on the total loss. In our experiments, we set the number of supervised attention heads to 1 (head index 0 in the chosen layer), and $\lambda = 1.0$, following the original setup by [19] and to avoid introducing additional hyperparameter tuning. Deep learning models have been trained using PyTorch⁶.

Model	Description
BiRNN[LIME]	Standard Bidirectional RNN without attention. Explanations from LIME.
BiRNN-Attn[LIME]	BiRNN with custom attention layer. Explanations from LIME.
BiRNN-Attn[Attn]	BiRNN with custom attention layer. Explanations from attention weights.
BiRNN-Ratn[LIME]	BiRNN trained with rationale supervision. Explanations using LIME.
BiRNN-Ratn[Attn]	BiRNN trained with rationale supervision. Explanations from attention weights.
mBERT[LIME]	Standard mBERT. Explanations from LIME.
mBERT[Attn]	Standard mBERT. Explanations from internal attention mechanism.
mBERT-Ratn[LIME]	mBERT trained with rationale supervision. Explanations using LIME.
mBERT-Ratn[Attn]	mBERT trained with rationale supervision. Explanations from internal attention weights.

Table 1: Description of model variants and explanation sources used in explainability evaluation.

⁶ <https://pytorch.org/>

4.3 Evaluation

Model performance has been recorded using macro-F1, accuracy, precision, and recall. Explainability of the models has been evaluated by comparing model extracted rationales with human-annotated rationales on two dimensions: plausibility and faithfulness [9]. Plausibility was evaluated using token F1-score, Area Under the Precision–Recall Curve (AUPRC) and Intersection over Union (IOU), and faithfulness using comprehensiveness and sufficiency. IOU, on a token level, is calculated by taking the size of the overlap of the tokens covered, divided by the size of the union. A prediction is counted as a match if the overlap with any of the ground truth rationales is more than a threshold of 0.5. These partial matches are then used to calculate an F1 score. Token precision measures how many were correct, of tokens model highlighted, and recall measures how many of the true rationale tokens were found. The token-F1 score is the harmonic mean of token precision and recall. Metrics designed for continuous or soft token-scoring models evaluate the ranking of tokens, rewarding models that assign higher scores to human-annotated rationale tokens. An example is AUPRC, which is constructed by sweeping a threshold over the token precision and recall scores. Faithfulness measures how well an explanation captures the model’s decision making process. If an XAI technique has extracted the top-k tokens that contribute to a prediction, comprehensiveness measures a change in model confidence for the same class after the top-k tokens are removed, and sufficiency measures the change in model confidence if only the top-k tokens are used for predictions. For a given MGY instance x_i , let $m(x_i)_j$ denote the model’s predicted probability for class j . Let r_i be the set of top- k rationale tokens selected by the explanation method. A contrastive input $x_i \setminus r_i$ is constructed by removing these tokens, while r_i alone forms an input consisting only of the rationale tokens. Comprehensiveness is measured as follows:

$$\text{Comprehensiveness} = m(x_i)_j - m(x_i \setminus r_i)_j \quad (2)$$

where $m(x_i)_j$ is the original model prediction and a contrasted sample for x_i

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
BiRNN	0.7975 ± 0.0068	0.7982 ± 0.0063	0.7975 ± 0.0068	0.7974 ± 0.0068
BiRNN-Attn	0.7527 ± 0.0197	0.7495 ± 0.0428	0.7689 ± 0.0564	0.7564 ± 0.0163
BiRNN-Ratn	0.7543 ± 0.0118	0.7610 ± 0.0336	0.7479 ± 0.0460	0.7522 ± 0.0068
mBERT	0.7952 ± 0.0091	0.7967 ± 0.0101	0.7952 ± 0.0091	0.7950 ± 0.0090
mBERT-Ratn	0.7975 ± 0.0068	0.7982 ± 0.0063	0.7975 ± 0.0068	0.7974 ± 0.0068

Table 2: Classification performance reported as mean ± standard deviation, averaged across 10 runs.

is created by removing top-k predicted rationales. It evaluates if the selected tokens actually contributed towards the prediction. For all plausibility metrics, the value ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating the best performance and 0 the lowest. Sufficiency, which measures how sufficient the selected tokens are in making the prediction, is similarly calculated as:

$$\text{Sufficiency} = m(x_i)_j - m(r_i)_j \quad (3)$$

Comprehensiveness and sufficiency range from -1 to +1. For comprehensiveness, a value closer to 1 is more desirable, suggesting that removing rationales lowers confidence, whereas a value of 0 indicates that the extracted rationales did not affect model performance. A negative value indicates that removing rationales increased confidence, which seems counterintuitive. A value closer to 0 is considered more desirable for sufficiency, as it indicates that the rationales alone almost sufficient for prediction.

5 Results and Analysis

The results of the experiment are recorded and analyzed in this section. Hypothesis testing has been performed to check if the results are statistically significance. The average length of comments belonging to the class ‘MGY’ was 25.50 and ‘NOT’ was 18.28. The mean count of tokens per comment for ‘MGY’ is 6.3, and top 3 words are ‘randi’, ‘bhosdi’ and ‘kuttiya’. Table 2 displays the accuracy, precision, recall, and macro-F1 score of deep learning architectures (BiRNN and mBERT) with and without rationale supervision, and table 3 shows the performance of models on the plausibility metrics, which measure how well model-generated rationales align with human-annotated rationales, and faithfulness metrics, which assess whether the identified rationales are impactful towards the model’s predictions. The classification metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score), have been averaged over 10 runs, and the rationale metrics have been averaged over 1000 comments of length 10 or more. Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation, where the mean reflects the average performance across runs and the standard deviation indicates the variability of the results. LIME and attention has been used to extract tokens for comparison with gold standard rationales. Overall, model performance is fairly similar for BiRNN and mBERT (f1 score = 0.7974), rationale supervision seems to have only marginally improved model performance. BiRNN-Ratn[LIME] achieves the highest token-F1 (0.5022 ± 0.1867) and the highest AUPRC of (0.6761 ± 0.2067), highlighting the effectiveness of rationale supervision. However, model comprehensiveness has decreased as a result of rationale supervision, which could be a trade-off of improved sufficiency, such as for mBERT[Attn] and mBERT-Ratn[Attn] (from 0.1717 to 0.2042). BiRNN-Ratn[LIME] achieves a negative sufficiency of -0.0105, suggesting that removing the extracted rationales improved prediction confidence, which could indicate bias. The improvement in macro-F1 for mBERT[Ratn] over vanilla mBERT is not statistically significant under either a paired t-test ($p = 0.356$) or a Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($p = 0.447$). Similarly, Rationale supervision does not significantly affect BiRNN-Attn (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p = 0.43$) classification performance, at a significance level of 0.05. However, for explainability metrics, a majority of the metrics show statistically significant improvement for every metrics for mBERT and BiRNN-Attn through the Wilcoxon signed-rank test at a significance level of 0.05, except for IoU for mBERT[LIME] and BiRNN-Ratn[LIME].

Model	Plausibility			Faithfulness	
	Token F1	IOU	AUPRC	Comp	Suff
BiRNN [LIME]	0.4858 ± 0.1836	0.2120	0.6402 ± 0.2062	0.2495 ± 0.3241	0.0654 ± 0.1532
BiRNN-Attn [LIME]	0.4955 ± 0.1879	0.2360	0.6630 ± 0.2076	0.4601 ± 0.2910	0.4601 ± 0.2910
BiRNN-Attn [Attn]	0.4786 ± 0.2799	0.3240	0.4653 ± 0.2167	0.0001 ± 0.0311	0.4019 ± 0.1707
BiRNN-Ratn [LIME]	0.5022 ± 0.1867	0.2400	0.6761 ± 0.2067	0.5776 ± 0.3380	-0.0105 ± 0.0867
BiRNN-Ratn [Attn]	0.4786 ± 0.2799	0.3240	0.4653 ± 0.2167	0.0004 ± 0.0167	0.4370 ± 0.1694
mBERT [LIME]	0.4580 ± 0.2097	0.2050	0.6323 ± 0.2238	0.3941 ± 0.3679	0.0675 ± 0.2548
mBERT [Attn]	0.4887 ± 0.1959	0.2300	0.6446 ± 0.2266	0.2374 ± 0.3416	0.1717 ± 0.3290
mBERT-Ratn [LIME]	0.4596 ± 0.2073	0.2120	0.6327 ± 0.2223	0.3914 ± 0.3814	0.0801 ± 0.2666
mBERT-Ratn [Attn]	0.4095 ± 0.2069	0.1310	0.5522 ± 0.2271	0.1840 ± 0.3128	0.2042 ± 0.3298

Table 3: Explainability results reported as mean ± standard deviation, averaged over 1000 samples.

6 Discussion

This section analyzes the study’s findings in relation to the hypotheses and research questions.

1. RQ-1: How does the incorporation of rationales impact the predictive performance of misogyny classifiers on classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and macro-F1 score?

Based on the findings of the study, rationale incorporation did marginally improve the f1-score of mBERT (from 0.7950 ± 0.0090 to 0.7974 ± 0.0068), while reducing the f1-score of BiRNN-Attn. However, the improvement was not statistically significant when evaluated through paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank test at a significance level of 0.05. The slight improve in model performance is consistent with the results reported in earlier studies [21], and but also its performance on explainability metrics [19]. Future scope of this study includes experimenting with a larger dataset and other model architectures such as CNN-GRU, XLM-RoBERTa, etc. This will allow us to come to a more generalizable conclusion.

2. RQ-2: How does the incorporation of rationales impact the performance of misogyny classifiers on plausibility and faithfulness metrics?

The findings suggest that rationale supervision also improved model performance on explainability metrics for both models, with the improvement being statistically significant at 0.05 for most metrics. mBERT [LIME] achieved the weakest performance on token-F1 (0.4580 ± 0.2097) and IoU (0.2050), which improved moderately with rationale supervision (0.4596 ± 0.2073 and 0.2120). However, comprehensiveness dropped for both models with rationale supervision while sufficiency, which aligns with previous findings [23].

Thus, the first hypothesis that incorporating human-annotated rationales during training of misogyny classifiers improves model performance on empirical metrics was rejected, as a significant difference was not observed for performance

metrics (macro-f1) through paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank test at a significance level of 0.05. The second hypothesis that rationale incorporation does improve alignment with human annotated rationales failed to reject, as Wilcoxon signed-rank test suggests that the difference in explainability scores were significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ for most explainability metrics. The future scope of this study is to experiment with more complex model architectures, perform extensive hyperparameter tuning, tune λ and τ to optimize model performance, and train on a larger dataset. This study has several limitations. The fine-grained labels were not incorporated into training, which could have resulted in the loss of information. Creation of human-annotated rationales is an expensive and time-consuming process, and other approaches such as rationale classifiers or prompt-based extracted might be more scalable for larger datasets.

7 Conclusion

Hate speech and misogyny classification using NLP models is an ongoing effort, with new studies exploring different types of architectures for monolingual, multilingual, and code-mixed settings. This study examined the performance of deep learning models on novel code-mixed misogyny detection dataset, and the impact of incorporating human annotated rationales in training. The future scope for this study is to explore multi-label misogyny classification, explore additional machine learning and deep learning architectures, and experiment with larger datasets for misogyny detection. Additionally, alternative techniques for rationale selection and incorporation, such as prompt-based extraction and rationale masking, will be implemented.

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